

How many long-term SA activities (lasting 1 month or more) have you completed?

2-3 don't remember

one: christmas basket MYP2

2

2

1

1

1

2

0

2 total across the years.

3

2

2

2 services actions 1-Christmas Hamper 2- Helping the theater

1

2

Around 3

1

1

About 3

1

1

2

2 long term SA

0

1

1 this year, 1 last year

3

2

1

0

2 or 3

2

1

Absolutely none.

0

1

0

	2
	0
	3
	0
	3
	0
None	
	1
	1
	1
	1
	1
	1
None	
	1
I have completed one SA activity lasting more than a month, and one SA activity that lasted more than a month but was a the creation of a presentation, so it does not count as a long term activity.	
	1
I have completed 1 long-term SA activity in had lasted 4 months	
One approved (but not completed)	
One	
2-3	
	2
	4

What was your most meaningful SA activity so far, and why?

To help clean the design room, it really needed a clean and I'm happy it looks much more organized now, it also gave me more motivation to clean my surroundings like my room for example female products in the bathroom MYP2 - it was very useful and helpful for the girls of our school since the basket was emptied in a matter of just a couple weeks.

Cleaning trash in some places because it helped the environment around me.

Teaching kids about AI cause it's important

christmas hamper for the school cleaner because it showed appreciation for their work

Swimming, as i like swimming and it was a fundraiser.

Helping the design teacher in designing some of the elements of the school play.

Caring for plants in MYP3, this was meaningful because i think it was well planned and actually helped build certain skills within our classmates.

Donating the money we earned

Volunteering at a cancer meet.

Christmas hamper, because we got to help staff by providing them with food and stuff

Giving people in my class plants to grow to establish a sense of responsibility

Probably the movie, as it impacted me the most by teaching me what a career in film might look like.

Helping last theater in school.

Introducing a new student to the school (buddy), this was meaningful as I was able to make the person feel home and welcomed at the school.

The letters for veterans because I found it really impactful

I would say gifting to the teachers, as I feel they are not appreciated often and should be more taken seriously of what they contribute to the students' education and lives in school.

Creating a website for cyberbullying to spread awareness, I think this helps a lot of teens at the moment since it's very common in this modern world

My second one where I fundraiser for the Salvation Army during family day—because it taught me the importance of international mindedness and to respect other cultures/countries.

Probably cleaning up trash around the neighbourhood and creating brochures to spread awareness.

Even though it is considered the „easy” service as action activity, I put way more effort into researching and connecting with the community than I usually do for the activities.

Making a Christmas Hamper for the cleaners because I got to go shopping

My most meaningful SA was helping the Cafe on Family Day. I think that this is the most meaningful because of the amount of people that there was to serve, and this might have been trickier for the cafe staff to serve alone.

gifting the teachers

My most meaningful SA so far was the Christmas hamper. This SA showed me that how hard the cleaners work in our school and we gifted them items that they would like and if I was a cleaner I would have felt so happy if I got these hampers.

N/A

It was making the Christmas hamper, to show the gratitude to the hardworking school cleaners.

The Family task, I wasn't meant to help, but I spent 5 hours helping my art teacher sell paintings of primary and secondary. It was unexpected and enjoyable.

Cleaning up neighbourhoods because it impacted the communities the most for the local ecosystems, and the members' health from removal of pollution.

Baking cookies for a disabled home, I felt useful

Donating

Taking care of a child, as it was my first time

No

MYP4: Coaching U14-1 basketball team. Long term task that gave me the most unique growth and experiences.

I am not sure

A sponsor cycle as it raised money to donate to children in need.

Babysitting

I don't remember

Rather not say

Helping to clean up the streets in Nepal

showing a new student around school, being their buddy, because it is one of the SaA that I truly believe made a difference for that person.

My most meaningful SA so far was a food drive I helped organise in MYP3 along with some of my classmates, because in the end we did raise a large amount of food and donated it to a well known organisation that then distributed the food to those in need in the community. This activity was the most meaningful to me because it had a real impact on people in the community and truly helped people in need.

It has not been done yet, however, I will participate in a 20km walk to raise funds. The walk is called xxxxx and I think it is most meaningful as it impacts the largest community which is the countries the program funds.

I think the Christmas hamper was the most meaningful SA i have done, as it taught me how the important the schools cleaners and helped me appreciate them.

Helping on Family Day, because I realized how hard it is to communicate with people younger than me.

Bottle donation money as it helped people without a home

The christmas basket

The ict evening because it was fun for me as well

The Christmas hamper, it felt like I was doing something for the community of the school.

Helping a new kid by being her buddy, this helped her because it was her first couple of weeks and she barely knew anyone or what is going on

Teaching art because now i know how to teach or where to start from in teaching (not very serious teaching)

Christmas hamper, because it helped the cleaner

I only did one and its about taking trash.

Making Christmas Hamper, because it was to appreciate the people who clean bathrooms after we go home.

The most meaningful SA Activity I did was serve warm food to the homeless population in xxxxx. I found this very meaningful because I managed to give those people warm meals, which they rarely enjoy as most meals they receive are cold. They enjoyed the food we gave them and complimented us. That's why it is the most meaningful activity I have completed.

The christmas hamper because it helped the cleaners

The Christmas Hamper because we had to do 5 chores and then give food basket to the cleaners of our school. This is the most meaningful because we spent a lot of time on this and we needed to do chores

The first one (helping cleaning and designing the park) since it also helped me with design and also gave the kids a better place to play.

I can not answer this question with any certainty.

S

It was helping my friend with her homework. I spent some time with her and enjoyed, at the same time I helped her with learning something

The long term group cleanup from this year

What could the school or SA Coordinator do to help you feel more engaged in SA?

Fun activities, more support for students who have no idea how to do sa

maybe give assemblies that give ideas

Give me support and some examples of SA activities

Give more opportunities

i don't know

Tutor period updates.

They could help the students if they do not understand what to do in service as action.

Link units and subjects to SA opportunities.

More

Not much, but to ensure that all the teachers regularly promote it over the year more often.

Maybe give us examples of how the activities we do can help the people around us

I feel that opportunities are given but they are usually divided into 2, either a very large activity or something to do with the school or school parties. I think a lot more could be done with the local community

Not really, as the school/SA Coordinator is not actually with me at the event if it is out of school so I still would just do it for the requirement of passing the school.

I helped with the drinks, it will be hard for only a person to do it so we needed more people to help us, and if I wasn't there the drinks would be worse than what happened.

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Im not sure

Give more ideas to do linked to the subjects, consistent check-ups for the progress if possible.

i think I'm fine.

(Don't know)

I really want to do something outside of school, like providing any help on farms, public facilities, etc. It is similar to volunteering, but by creating opportunities and reaching out to healthcare areas and different events (like raising money), it can make service as action more interesting and motivating, knowing that we are supporting a good cause (and is not repetitive). Reaching out so myself is difficult due to the language barrier.

More SA activities recommended

I think more opportunities for SA completions in school would motivate me to feel more engaged in the concept.

have constant links with SA and the subjects being taught in school

I feel that the schools could come up with more activities or school programmes to help a few students help them for their SA.

Maybe more opportunities in school to do SA's related to or linked to subjects.

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Nothing

Im not sure

Give a relatable reason to do SA

Not sure

Recommend more variable activities

Encourage the students more

Incentivise the completion more than it currently is.

I am not sure

Refer to it more in class and teachers link it to their own class.

Nothing

Idk

If SA was one large community service that you do with classmates, (eg: building a retaining wall or planting trees) instead of a few smaller activities I think it would be more memorable and do more good for the community than having the students run around individually picking up trash, helping setup parties, or raise money for charity. To summarize, I think having the students of an entire class work together and decide on a large community goal while setting a date beforehand is a much better way for them to learn. When you tell them that helping someone else do XYZ will give them a SA, you are inadvertently making them feel like helping the community is something they are forced to do, which may make them less willing to do so in the future. As much as I wish it were so, you cannot force someone to be selfless and productive within their community. I think the whole SA system needs reworking.

Nothing really, maybe you can give rewards for each SaA completed to each student, or there could be a point system connecting to the houses that was introduced this term where each SaA or CAS completed gives an extra 10 points (can be changed).

The SA Coordinator could maybe try providing examples of different organizations that would allow MYP students (i.e teenagers) to volunteer and/or help do something meaningful for the community (perhaps categorized by long term or short term).

Include SA ideas in classes.

Maybe the SA coordinator can help provide more service as action opportunities to students.

Giving more examples/ideas on an activity

Special 'rewards' for completing the early

Idk

Maybe give us a small reward at the end of the year

Explain how these actions could make someone really or happy or make their day.

Give more feedback and expect less from us

No feedback

Nothing.

Give us more time? I dont know

I don't know.

The SA Coordinator could help arrange class SA activities once every year. Another system that could work is that the School collects 3 Euros from every parent and gives one euro to the child after completing one SA. This could help other students feel more engaged in SA. I myself am very engaged in SA.

I don't really know

They could have done more exciting and like brining for example if you volunteer to do this Then we will put a special thanks on your report card.

I would say maybe check the SA faster.

give more accurate feedback and respond to my messages in our personal correspondence faster (not a week after I sent the letter)

No idea

Maybe it would be useful to give some ideas for SA.

Nothing
